

Interpreting Consumer Preferences: Evaluating the Role of Promotion Mix on Customer Preference of Consumer Durables in National Capital Region

Ghanshyam Sharma

Ph.D Scholar, School of Management and Commerce, K.R. Mangalam University

Dr. Avjeet Kaur

Ph.D, Assistant Professor, School of Management and Commerce, K.R. Mangalam University

Dr. Bikramjit Rishi

Ph.D, Postdoc (EU Fellow) Associate Professor, Institute Of Management Technology

Abstract:

In this technology-driven era, there has been an extensive augmentation in the reliance on electronic products like television, air-conditioner, online-streaming videos, advertising, movies, internet, e-books and magazines, etc. Several times, the consumers don't buy products to suffice their needs, rather they buy these under the influence of advertisements and sometimes owing to peer comparison. For the promotion of a product, advertisements and building brand image have therefore held high importance among the marketers. Promotion is nothing but the seller initiated efforts to persuade and promote an idea of selling the goods and services. The current study aims to evaluate the role of different promotional strategies and factors affecting consumer preference of consumer durables in the national capital region. It is believed that sales promotion is vital to the promotion mix and is targeted upon the consumers attempted at higher market acquisition making it mandatory in the field of marketing. The study relies on secondary data, where the existing body of literature pertaining to promotional mix and its impact on consumer purchase decision has been critically evaluated, for arriving upon valuable conclusions. The study found that the literature sufficiently supports that all the components of promotion mix influence consumer preferences in some or the other way. Based on the findings, the research also provides valuable recommendations towards enhancement of the advertising and brand image techniques for the electronics industry, and proposes a conceptual framework that can be further validated through future research.

Keywords: Promotion mix, consumer durables, consumer buying behavior, brand image techniques.

INTRODUCTION

The term brand is a set of tangible and intangible attributes designed to create awareness, identity on the products, persons, organization or services (Bonnici, 2015). Branding is the long term strategy ranging from product innovation to marketing communications. Brands are constantly evolving concepts which act as the best tool in promotion and expansion of a business. A brand can be defined as the sum of the characteristics of a product or service as perceived by the user. Thus, a brand is associated with a specific name, image or plan, or all, or a combination of these-that is made use to popular a specific company's product or service. There are various definitions of brand in marketing literature. Brand has been defined as 'Any name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies a seller's goods or services as distinct from that of other sellers'. In legal terms, brand is preferably called as trademark. . One item, one family or all the families of goods or services may be identified as a brand. (American Marketing Association AMA, 2007). When it comes to the Indian landscape, a shopper's inclination towards better quality products have been raising consistently due to the expansion in wage and sociological strengths that have influenced the elevated needs to lead life in a superior manner. A brand can be characterized as a merchant's guarantee to give reliably one of a kind arrangement of attributes, favorable circumstances, and administrations to the buyers" (Rajasekar & Srinivasan, 2018).

According to Durrani, Godil, Baig, and Sajid (2015), there exists a practical link between brand image and teenager consumer buying behavior. The globalised business scenario is a foot forward in strengthening the brand image of organizations. In pursuance of acquiring identification and a brand position in the trade sector, organizations employ diverse methods by which consumer's behavior and apprehension develops. This kind of astuteness is known as Brand image. However, this perception gives either a positive or a negative brand image/ brand positioning has the potential to improve/destroy the overall performance of the brand as the consumer preferences rely heavily on it. Consumers segregate and produces an image analogous to the brand.. Such images are gauged against a variety of points to be referred, namely, appropriate social image, product category image, social image, ideal social image, self-image, ideal self-image, to assess brand by consumers' reactions inclusive of brand attitude, brand preference, and brand loyalty.

Theoretically, brand image is a wide concept related to companies, businesses, their goods, products or services, and is distributed into various categories: corporate image, brand image, product image, and store image. Forming an image in consumer's mind is done by combining the constituents of identity at the brand level. (Nagar,2015). Consumers give huge importance to brands as owning different brands is associated with higher status and prestige. Their views on brands expect superior quality of brands and have different perspective. Within the specific time frame, if a brand satisfies the needs of the customer then they become devoted to the brand and develop a dedicated relationship. It is a well-known fact that, customer satisfaction is a major precedence in any organization.. The goods and services available in the market help consumers to fulfill their desires and needs. . Hence, studying the behavior of the consumers is another significant task for producers and marketers (Riaz, 2015).

Adnan, Nordin, and Rahman (2017) assessed the factors affecting Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs)/Electric vehicles (EVs) adoption. For reducing harmful carbon emissions, important steps, the collective outcome of 'hyperbolic discounting' is discussed by the study and it has a direct effect on consumers' environmental concern. . Grimmer, and Miles (2017) studied the intention-behavior gap in pro-environmental consumer behavior. Results of their study revealed that implementation intentions mediated the relationship between intention and pro-environmental consumer behavior.

According to Richardson, Ganz, and Vallone (2015), "online banner/video advertising is a tactic mainly used to advertise e-cigarettes and cigars rather than cigarettes, some with unproven claims about benefits to health. Given the reach and accessibility of online advertising to vulnerable populations such as youth and the potential for health claims to be misinterpreted, online advertisements need to be closely monitored". Similarly, Fitchett, and Caruana (2015) stated that "in the analysis of consumption and consumer behavior, descriptive analysis (DA) will often be an appropriate response simply due to its textual, representational and ideological features."

IMPACT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

A study conducted on the impact of green marketing on consumer buying behaviors in Kolkata is conducted by Sen (2014). To gather the primary data, a sample of 100 respondents were taken from Kolkata.. The results of their study emphasized that the consumer purchase decisions in Kolkata are not influenced by the green marketing practices performed by the companies. However, the consumers wanted to pay an extra bit for the 'green' products, owing to the higher value associated with these. Hence, the companies sell the products at higher prices if they can enhance the product's performance and are able to offer products that render value addition to the consumers.

Pappas (2016) studied the marketing strategies, identified risks, and consumer trust in online buying behavior. The researcher highlighted that besides the rapid increase in online shopping, there is no definite knowledge about the perceived risk factors, the effect and influence of marketing on product and web vendor consumer loyalty.. In this paper, the researcher focused on holidaymakers' perspectives with the aid of bookings by internet by for their holidays.. An association between internet perceived risks and the influence of product and e-channel risks were confirmed by the findings.. Online purchase intentions which are constantly influenced by the products along with e-channel consumer trust are determined by this study. Age old patterns of human communication still exist. The cross cultural differences in interpersonal and mass communication for creating awareness is necessary to study the way media functions are performed and advertisements works. In one culture, advertising is persuasive by nature; whereas in another, it is meant to impart trust between the companies and the consumers. The pattern of advertising will not be the same in every culture .Thus, patterns for how advertising works in one culture cannot be generalized to all other cultures. Various verbal and non-verbal communication styles are recognized in both interpersonal and mass communication. In such culture clusters, one or the other style prevails.(Mooij, 2018).

IMPACT OF PROMOTION MIX ON CUSTOMER PREFERENCES

Gunasekaran, Basha, and Lakshmana (2016) explored the impact of promotion mix of DTH (Direct To Home) manufacturers on the customer behavior with regard to Vellore District Tamil Nadu. The paper revealed that the increasing use of sales promotions which created an impact on consumers. It also focused on how to be prone to deals and how it motivated marketers, thus, resultantly leading to rely on sales promotions and helps in supporting consumers from competitors' products.. Apart from that, there are also major external factors like socio-economic, regulatory and technological issues that altered both the structure of DTH service industry as well as the form of competition within it.

Kumar and Patra (2017) studied the contribution of promotion mix in enhancing the brand equity. The authors reviewed the significant promotional mix elements which include personal selling, direct marketing, advertising, public relations, and sales promotion to brand equity dimensions. The research findings revealed that promotional mix component facilitates enhancement in the brand equity. However, the study also suggested that monetary promotion might harm brand image posing a threat on brand equity creation. Additionally, they found that digital marketing has a major role in building brand equity via brand image and brand association. Thus, this study strongly emphasizes that promotional mix factors help to enhance brand equity. To enhance the brand equity, the organization must increase their promotional activities' budget. Once the organization succeeds in raising the promotional activities, their brand equity will be involuntarily high.

IMPACT OF BRAND IMAGE ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR (HOME-APPLIANCES)

Ray and Choudhury (2015) studied on consumer decision making for purchasing certain home appliance products. The study attempted to judge the factors based on which a market is segmented such as demographics (gender, age, occupation, education), followed by psychographic characteristics (lifestyle, social class, personality, behavioral values, status and convenience), self-concept and its effect on customers' decision making. The researchers have sampled people associated with management education from Kolkata, segmented by. It revealed the interrelation between the independent and dependent variables listed above. , i.e. purchase intention. Further, it presented that 'psychographic' is the most important market segmentation factor. It also revealed occupation, lifestyle and values as being the most important factors that affect people's buying intentions. In this study, the researchers empirically studied the customers' decision making by external and internal factors.

Rath (2017) examined the internal and external factors influencing the consumer buying behavior in the washing machine segment. The findings show that the demographic factors did not affect the satisfaction level of the consumers. In this research, the regions Cuttack and Bhubaneswar were taken as the sample areas, targeting 200 respondents from various retail malls/ retail outlets of the electronic products. It was found that the source of information to purchase Washing Machine majorly consists of the friends, relatives, newspaper and TV.

Manhas and Tukamushaba (2015) provided customers' expectations and their understanding along with other factors that strengthen service experience at the time of guest stay in the selected three, four-star hotels in Jammu, Chandigarh and Delhi. The research outcomes highlighted that guest' expectations and actual experiences are at disparity. Proper recommendations to the hotel owners especially, and the hospitality sector overall were made by the researcher which aimed at improving customer's memorable experience. The study employed a questionnaire structured to collect data from the hotel managers as well as the individual customers. The guests' attitude, their expected and unexpected suggestions for analyzing the important information facilitates to find areas critical to customer service quality.

Braithwaite, Densley-Tingley, and Moreno (2015) explored whether energy levels of washing machines should be extended to have insights on durability, as this could help customers in making a decision not only on energy or cost but in terms of lifespan of the product.. Moreover, to understand if there is any positive interrelation the existing manufacturer guarantees can provide an indication of the expected durability of the product and this is investigated. Since washing machine is one of the key household appliances, it can be found in majority of the houses. The study mentioned that "Energy efficiency ratings are provided as a method for consumers to make an informed purchasing decision and were brought in by EU legislation to reduce energy use and enable users to reduce running costs, as it is known that the greater environmental impact of a washing machine is during use".

FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

Joshi and Rahman (2015) studied the attitude-behavior inconsistencies in the context of green purchasing. In this research, the researcher determined various motives, possible explanations for inconsistencies reported in green purchase behavior provided explanation of the barriers affecting decision making of customers.. These factors were characterized as being unique to the individual decision maker and those are considered situational. Thus, the paper reveals the significant predictors of consumer green purchase behavior, which will help the lawmakers and managers in developing and implementing strategies to motivate green purchasing.

Badgaiyan and Verma (2014) examined the effects of five intrinsic factors; personality, culture, materialism, shopping enjoyment tendency, and impulsive buying tendency on impulsive buying behavior. Here, the researcher used structural equation modeling and collected data from 508 consumers covering different parts of India's National Capital Region. The results showed a positive significant relationship is influenced by the three constructs of materialism, that is, shopping enjoyment tendency, and impulsive buying tendency.

Jung, Shim, Jin, and Khang (2016) studied and examined factors (for instance, ad values and social networking advertising characteristics) influencing consumers' attitudes and behavioral intention. The research findings showed that significant impacts on attitude and behavioral intention was significantly impacted by peer influence among all forms of Social Networking Advertising (SNA). Additionally, the results suggested that attitudes towards the advertisement played a mediating role between SNA characteristics and behavioral intention.

Yadav and Pathak (2016) aimed to understand green product buying behavior by young customers in developing India.. The researchers handled the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a theoretical framework. The data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire survey and analyzed with the help of structural equation modeling (SEM). The outcomes stated the young consumers' intention for purchasing green products asserting to the usefulness of TPB.

Singh and Singh (2016) studied the effectiveness of online advertising. They concluded that the impact of online advertising on consumer buying behavior increased other forms of advertising. The majority of the respondents accepted that online advertisement are almost everywhere on internet. Mirabi, Akbarieh, and Tahmasebi Card (2015) aimed to investigate the factors affecting the purchase intention of Bono brand tile consumers. Here, a researcher-made questionnaire with 25 questions. The research results revealed that the product quality is affected by variables of product quality, brand advertising and shows the highest impact on customers' purchase intention. It was however understood that the two variables of packaging and price didn't have a significant impact on customers' purchase intention. Wilkinson et al., (2015) presented a novel application of an optimization approach used to estimate dietary changes in the UK. The work also covers the use of data on consumer behavior for the potential acceptability. Social media advertising sketches a new dimension to advertising offering a platform to interact with users. It is found that there is a high percentile of correlation between variables that collect and exchange information through Facebook. Here, the study highlights significant implications for companies that make use of Facebook advertising among other advertising strategies. The study further mentioned that to experience the full potential of Facebook advertising; they should give customized messages to the customers, gives incentives and promotions to motivate them (Dehghani, & Tumer, 2015).

FRAMEWORK AND PREPOSITIONS

Grewal, Bart, Spann, and Zubcsek (2016) provided a framework to formulate the current findings in mobile advertising, and also devise a research agenda to build extra work in this field. 1) Nature of industry, 2) Firm's ability to deliver mobile advertising, 3) Rapidly increasing variety in mobile devices, 4) To facilitate and increase access to mobile inventory, 5) Government and industry regulations can have a substantial effect. In another paper, Zhang, Cao, Ho, and Chow (2017) presented new models and algorithms for object-level video advertising. The proposed framework is: 1) Using a threshold-based method that relies on the HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradient) features, performing a shot segmentation; 2) Use of discriminatively trained part-based models for object detection; 3) Formulating and solving an optimization problem that considers both ads' attractiveness and intrusiveness to viewers for optimization based object selection; 4) Retrieval of ads by using two strategies, i.e., clothing retrieval for human and category-based retrieval for other detected objects.

Ghose and Todri (2015) measured the impact of display advertising on online consumer behavior. They found that even minute exposure to display advertising can increase users' ideals to find the brand and the corresponding product; consumers involved in active search to collect information via search engines and through direct visits to the advertiser's website. They also revealed that there was four times increase in the advertising performance. Here the consumers are targeted in the purchasing platform and was found that as

the duration of exposure was increased, the consumers engage more in direct searches rather than indirect searches. Wharton, Foth, and Choi (2014) identified factors that promote consumer behavior causing expired domestic food waste. Three factors are proposed namely, supply knowledge, location knowledge, and food literacy. These influence consumers' behavior and give new insights to the existing literatures.

GM and Nirmala (2017) proposed a Hybrid e-Advertising framework and is designed with the aid of Concurrent Mobile Agents and provides an environment for processing simultaneously the advertiser requests to address issues of one-to-many and many-to-many mapping between the advertisers and the ad-publisher sites. It is found that the framework is more efficient and dynamic, and the implementation is best suitable for small number of advertisers to publish the advertisements. Similarly, in another research, the authors provided insights into suitable advertisement based on their preferences for the people. The main goal is to build an advertisement framework that is supported by target advertising. This is done by analyzing social network content. This information is then used to predict the advertisement categories that interest a particular user. (Perera et al.,2014).

THEORIES ON PROMOTIONAL MIX

It has become significant for the marketers to make critical decisions regarding the promotional plans. Promotional tools employed in the field of business strike their strengths, weaknesses and marketing budget. Experienced marketer well knows about the theories and practices to be adopted in the marketing field. One strategy which could be followed by the researcher is push-pull strategy. In the 'push' strategy, the sales force propels the products to the wholesalers and they push it to the retailers, whereas in the 'pull' strategy depending highly on marketing communications to create awareness and inclination. . Thus, it pulls the customers into the stores to purchase the products. The other promotional mix is the advertising or public relations strategy where in the former one the marketers exaggerate and the phenomena are well understood by the consumers. The consumers are well aware that the advertisement strategy misleads the consuming public. On the other hand, public relation is free unlike the former one and is interactive in nature (Biz Fluent).

Promotion Mix theory can be a turning point to the study includes advertising, public relations, personal selling and sales promotion. These are used to produce organizational sales goals, profits and to communicate with the targeted market. Promotion Mix theory can be a turning point to which consists advertising, public relations, personal selling and sales promotion. They are used as tools to communicate to the target market and produce organizational sales goals and profits. This theory of promotional mix will help the study to evaluate the role of promotional mix on customer preference of consumer durables in the National Capital Region.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY AND DISCUSSION

Owing to the globalised scenario, cut throat competition, where every marketer is struggling to acquire a higher share of customers and increasing rationality of the customers, there is an increasing need for the marketers to study and understand the purchasing behavior of consumers. A knowledge of the factors influencing consumer purchase intentions will assist the marketers in formulating effective is said to be influenced by advertising and brand image strategies. For instance, advertisements for children should ideally be posted either afternoon or early morning hours. It is noted likewise because during these hours of the day children watch maximum television. In one of the researches, it was revealed that the facilitating factors of product quality, brand advertising and name had the biggest impact on customers' purchase intention; at the same time, the variables of packaging and price didn't create any impact on consumers' purchase intention. It is clear from these findings that the consumers rely more on quality and advertising, rather than packaging and cost of the product.

Similarly, in another study, most of the direct and indirect path effects were conveyed as constant. The study also highlighted brand image, perceived price, and perceived value as the three most important determinants which directly affect the consumers' purchase intentions. Direct and mediating effects of brand image, price, trust, and value on consumers' booking intentions as well as the comparison of gender differences in online hotel booking was examined by the researches.. Hence, the study accentuated that it is essential to develop a strong trust among customers and making constant efforts towards the improvement of their perceived price and value associated to the overall product or service provided by the company.

Thus, studying consumers' preference is highly crucial for seeking consumer's attention, and building trust. Understanding the consumer's needs is really important when it comes to producing the right advertisement for the right audience. Overload of information dilutes the purpose of the advertisement itself. They will never buy the product and it might also lead to a creation of a wrong perception in their minds towards the company and the brand.

Conceptual Framework

This review is an attempt towards perceiving the effect of promotional mix on consumer preferences of consumer durables in the National capital region of India. It will also assist in discerning the recognition level of consumers on the promotional mix of consumer durables and the major affecting components of the promotional mix that influence consumer purchase decision concerning the consumer durables. For this purpose, the key constructs of this study and their associations were identified by the researcher which have been presented underneath. Taking into consideration the review of literature, below framework demonstrates the relationship between the constructs identified. Since the framework has not been empirically validated and is based on the researcher's understanding of the literature pertaining to the topic, future research attempting the validation of the developed framework would be useful.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Author

Singh & Cole (1993) in their study reported the results of a study where they examined the comparative efficacy of 15 and 30-second advertisements by utilizing novel advertisements that had different messages associated with them for the viewers (informational against emotional). They employed a sample of 138 undergraduates many times and applied multiple dependent variables. It was found that Informational 15 second advertisements were as capable as informational 30-second advertisements in various situations. On the other hand, emotional 30-second advertisements were found to be higher to emotional 15-second commercials which determined a customer's brand learning and behavior towards a brand.. Hence, it may be observed from this study that time and duration of an advertisement influences advertising efficiency which in turn effects positioning of a brand and further consumer preferences. Several other authors (Assmus et al.,1984; Houston et al., 1987; Brown et al., 1998; Wells et al., 2003; Danaher et al., 2008) asserts the multiple variables that influence advertising effectiveness. According to the authors, advertising effectiveness depends extensively on product trial, graphics and verbal components of an advertisement, advertising strategies of the competitors, and the length of an advertisement. According to Jakstiene, et al. (2008) advertisements mould the responses of the people towards a brand through discernment, i.e. the knowledge related to the opinion of an individual concerning the information conveyed through ads. The individual perceives these cognitions through his senses, attention, perception, memory, language, reasoning etc. Whether at retail or a corporate level, advertising plays a rudimentary role in developing a brand image. It acquaints consumers about the practical capacities of the brand while concurrently instilling the brand with its symbolic values and interpretations pertinent to the consumer (Meenaghan, 1995).

Further, it is also felt that public relations and the ways through which a business publicizes information to

all its stakeholders have a major role to play in positioning a brand in the mind of the consumers. Public relations emphasizes on conveyance credibility with the audiences that have impacts on the business results namely from media analysts, bureaucrats and influencers on policy, consumers and stakeholders. Power and value of an organization's brands to all the shareholders is an essential element. Numerous aspects such as brand of the corporate, from timber and characters, emotional and functional benefits, end goal and core message are in full leverage with the external as well as internal audiences that raise credibility and performance (Mikáčová & Gavlaková, 2014). Moreover, the literature extensively has outlined that the role of sales promotion in positioning a brand in the mind of the customers cannot be undermined. In fact, it has been witnessed and empirically established by some of the researchers that consumers tend to shift brands based on the offers and discounts being given. The findings of Chandon, Laurent and Wansink (2000) mentioned that promotion done in sales might lead to fruitful results in regards to consumers that are needed beyond price prudence. . Many consumers switch brands to receive better deals that build and enhance their rational buyer self-perception, and these consumers are favorably prone to promotions, i.e. these consumers will always attempt to give a hand on a new product or service that is being promoted well. Hence, all these factors taken together, i.e. advertising, public relations and sales promotion assist in building brand image, exposure, awareness and credibility in the minds of the consumers, thus, positioning a brand well.

Next, another important element of the promotion mix, i.e. personal selling is observed as an imperative variable directly evoking consumer preference. Muna & Zennie(2010) reported that salespersons' credibility, patience in dealing with customers, commitment to the promises and associated mien had an imminent influence on the consumer content. Merchandiser's present in-store has a imperative role in acquiring consumers with all associated facts that impact their purchase resolution. Azam et al. (2016) and Kumar et al. (2011) illustrated the promotion in sales and advertising had collectively with the brand image, which had been able to position itself in influencing consumer buying decision to a great extent. Moreover, it's the price of the product and the quality that affects the consumers' preference for a good over others.

Summing up the review on the theoretical framework developed, it may be inferred here that advertising is influenced by various factors such as competitor's strategies, visual appeal and aesthetics, product trials and schemes advertised and most importantly, the time and duration of an advertisement. Further, advertising along with company's image (communication effectiveness with its stakeholders and ways of publicizing) and sales promotion measures have a significant role to play in positioning a product, service or brand in the minds of the customer. It is up for no further debate that the manner in which a brand is positioned in the minds of the consumer determines the consumer preference of a particular good. The literature also supports that the fourth element of the promotion mix, i.e. personal selling directly influences the purchase decision of a consumer. Last but not the least, the perceived value and quality of a product or service also contribute to the consumer purchasing decision. Hence, all the elements of the promotion mix have been supported by the literature as being the contributors towards determining consumer preferences.

CONCLUSION

Based on the reviewed literature that majorly covered impact of advertisement on consumer buying behavior; impact of brand image on consumer buying behavior; factors affecting consumer buying behavior; theoretical framework and propositions, it was found that consumers intend to spend more on green products, which are organic and eco-friendly. Apart from advertising and brand image, quality plays a major role. However, the companies need to build effective business strategies including advertising in social media, electronic media, print media, and so on. Similarly, in one of the studies, the results revealed factors such as quality of the product, advertisement of the brand and its name had a significant impact on the purchase decisions of customers' which however had two variables namely packaging and the price which showed highest impact level on the purchase intention of customers.

When it comes to framework and propositions, the literature presents that emerging companies target on the goals of advertising and accounting pertaining to market factors in market environment. They aim to embed content-relevant advertisements within a video stream. The researchers have demonstrated the efficacy of the given method for object based video advertising. Apart from that, certain frameworks practiced in organizations are more efficient and dynamic in nature. It is highly essential to expand the market size at the same time decrease the complexities. Thus, the authors in their respective studies provided adequate insights into suitable advertisement for people built on their desire. Their main objective has been to aid in the development of a framework for advertisement that aids in chosen advertisement through the analysis of content in social network.

Based on the theoretical framework developed, it was established through this review that all the components of the promotion mix assist in determining the consumer preferences. The literature suggests that increased advertising, public relations (company's image) and sales promotion renders higher brand

positioning which in turn influences consumer's decision to buy a product or service. Personal selling, on the other hand, is deemed to directly influence consumer preference of a particular brand along with brand image/identity (positioning), perceived value and quality of a particular product or service. However, since the framework has not been empirically validated and is based on the researcher's understanding of the literature about the topic, future research attempting the validation of the developed framework would be useful.

Further, it's the decision making knack within consumer time investment, wealth and labor associated with questions such as what, why, how often and when pertaining to the purchase of products revealed the consumer preferences in durable products. The consumer preference would also depend on evaluation of the purchase made and how will their future spending be driven on durable products. So, studying consumer preference is an inevitable part for every organization. It helps the organization to learn, experiment, evaluate, and grow. This eventually makes the organization to be customer-oriented and adopt an evidence-based and highly-competitive approach.

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